

Initiation-Response-Feedback Interaction in Reading of Narrative Text during Online Class Grade VIII in SMP Gajah Mada

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ABSTRACT

The aims of the study was to state clearly the objectives of the study which is related with the problem of the study according to the IRF pattern. The Objectives is to describe what types and how IRF pattern in the classroom interaction in Reading narrative text was. The descriptive qualitative method was used in this study. Three methods were used to acquire data, those are: observation, video recording and interviewing. the subject of this study was students in 8th grade of SMP Gajah Mada. The data was examined using Sinclair and Coulthard theory in 1975. The result of this study were the following (1) The type of IRF pattern used in classroom interaction in Online Class based on Sinclair and Coulthard 1975 is used all, such as: Initiation, Response, and Feedback. (2) The realization of the IRF pattern itself already used in the classroom. Teacher always start the conversation in the class with Initiation, as the first way to get students Responses, after teacher get responses from the students, teacher will give some feedback whether is it correct or no. In the classroom, both the teacher and the students employed unbalanced language. Only 37% teacher and students use English, while 63% use Bahasa.

INTRODUCTION

Interaction is social process that happened in society which needed a communication to reach the goal, between one individual and another, between one group and another, which always needed a reciprocal relation. In society, interaction is a process that built a relation and makes one another become bound and comfort to make a conversation.

Interaction in classroom is the action and reaction conducted between teacher and students in classroom to build a relationship and communication well. The interaction itself using language as the tools and the mediator to make the conversation held to the others. That relation becomes good when one another using a simple conversation or language to make other easy to understood the meaning of the speaker to the listener. The classroom interaction is occurring from the beginning until the end of the class and teacher as the main actor to build a good interaction. When teacher starts convey the topic, the interaction happen when teachers invite students to answer teacher's question. The good interaction in the class also makes the students feel interest to receive the material and they become easy to develop their willingness to learn. If the teacher able to bring the class comfort, student emotion will stimulate the brain to receive lesson easy.

Undoubtedly, Interaction in classroom also refers to the IRF (Initiation-Response-Feedback). These patterns begin with initiation, with the first turn being a greeting or a question from the teacher. The student's response to the teacher's initiation is the second turn. Continue with feedback from the teacher after the student's response. The purpose of feedback is to provide an assessment or a reaction to the pupils' second turn (Lee,2007). The student response should be confirmatory by the teacher called feedback whether it is correct or not. (IRF) Initiation-Response-Feedback is the biggest interaction or communication that happened in classroom between students and teachers. The teacher initiates, learner responds, teacher gives feedback (Sinclair & Coulthard, 1975).

Initiation-response-feedback is the way for the teacher and students make a discussion or change opinion about the material to build a comprehension. As explain above when the students become passive the condition need teacher role to build an interaction by giving an initiation. So this is the certain way of IRF pattern in the classroom. It starts from the initiation about the student interest about something, continue with the students responses about teacher initiation and the teacher feedback about students respond.

Initiation-response-feedback (IRF) is a way between teacher and students make a discussion or change their opinion about the material to build a comprehension. In this interaction, teacher role and teacher control almost appear in classroom. Teacher may take a big control to handle the students interest in learn the lesson. From this pattern, teacher takes 2 main point those are in initiation and feedback.

Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are four abilities that need be learned in language teaching and learning, even for teachers and students to

communicate. Reading is beneficial for language acquisition, according to Harmer (2007: 99). There are several styles of reading, according to Patel & Praveen (2008), including intensive reading, extensive reading, reading aloud, and silent reading. Intensive reading is reading that focuses on idioms and terminology that the teacher has taught in the classroom and that can be found in a poem, novel, or other source. Extensive reading is a style of reading in which students read literature for pleasure and to improve their overall reading skills. Reading aloud entails speaking loudly and clearly. Silent reading, on the other hand, is designed to teach pupils how to read silently so that they may focus their attention or think about the texts.

Assuming that pupils comprehend what they have read, the more they read, the better they will get at it. The reading skill improved the kids' comprehension and provided some word knowledge. So, if the students do not grasp the content presented by the teacher, they will ask the teacher, and this is how the dialogue and IRF interaction in the classroom develop. However, in this study, the researcher concentrated on reading because it is when pupils begin to read a book that their curiosity emerges.

In teaching and learning process, there are some text that should taught to the students. This research focuses on the narrative text, because it need the students participant and they should comprehend the text specifically and require the students to overall read the text. Anderson (1997: 8) defines narrative as "a piece of writing that tells a tale and entertains or instructs the reader or listener." So, narrative text is type of text that entertains the reader and the content is contain so many information to the reader. But, some of the students not really like to read this text, because this combines many paragraphs.

Different from other research, this research focuses in online class as a place for teacher and students make an interaction. Nowadays the teaching and learning not should be held in face-to-face, but also can using a media to convey the lesson. An **online class** is a course conducted over the Internet. Computer-based learning, web-based learning, virtual classrooms, and digital collaborations are all examples of online learning, which is a subset of distant education that encompasses a wide range of technological applications and learning processes (Urdu and Weggen 2000). Shortly, online class is the process conveying the lesson using the media to build the interaction.

In teaching narrative text, initiation-response-feedback actually need, because by this pattern the teacher can invite students to communicate even using Bahasa Indonesia. In this way, teacher also can fixed the students pronunciation which used a wrong way to speak. Even in Online class phenomenon, actually teacher can more active to make students speak, by making some offer, for example when students can answer what teacher ask, they will given high score, even using other offer. Reading narrative text needs the teacher creativity to stimulate students critical thinking, even using a media to make students more interest in learning.

The teacher initiation to start the conversation even the online English class in reading narrative text to invite the students respond in English actually

good at the beginning. But when the teacher enters to the question relate to material, the students silent dominantly. Not only that, by the passive of the students, they will not confident with their ability in English, even they was lean in years. Here the simple conversation that happen in the classroom:

T : What do you got from the story that you read? Apa yang kamu dapat? Ada yang tau setelah membaca ceritanya?

S : (Silent)

T : Anyone can answer? I'll give you a gift. Yang bisa menjawab saya kasih hadiah

S : (Silent)

According to the researcher's first observation, the common interaction occurred in the classrooms is the teacher initiation and teacher feedback. In reading narrative text in the online class, the students not really active and mostly passive and just interested with teacher explanation and the story. It started from teacher initiation to stimulate students willingness, after that teacher will gave the question to start the conversation, and it will make the first interaction to the students, and the dominant process is the teacher talking in the classroom. Discern this situation, that when teacher talk more in the classroom, it makes the students become passive. It might be caused by many reasons that make the classroom interaction not balance, even the students have learn English in years since they are in elementary school. In conversation, even teacher or students mostly used Bahasa.

So, this is the reason why the researcher wants to research this problem, and see what teacher and research do to realize the IRF pattern in the classroom to increase the students interesting in reading a narrative text and increase their comprehension. The researcher's goal in this study is to characterize the IRF pattern and see if it has an impact on the learning activities outcomes in an online class. That is why the researcher used the Sinclair and Coulthard IRF model to analyze the pattern of reading narrative material in online class interactions between students and teachers.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

1. Classroom Discourse Analysis

When language is used in interpersonal communication, we obtain classroom discourse. Discourse analysis is study language in use: written texts of all kinds, and spoken data, from conversation to highly institutional forms of talk. Another definition mention that discourse analysis is a general term for a number of approaches to analyze written, spoken, sign language use or any significant semiotic event. Even if the communication is successful, we usually do not consider communication that does not entail competent verbal speaking to be discourse. When a child stamps his foot and begins to cry when instructed to come in for supper, the meaning I don't want to can be deduced, but it has not yet been expressed in language. Here the expert of the discourse analysis will make the structure of that language to catch the meaning. To find the meaning, we have to analyze first the context with the expert theory to make sure. The aspects of speech (including gaze, gesture, and movement) or writing

that are arguably regarded relevant in the context and pertinent to the claims the analysis is aiming to make form the basis of a discourse analysis.

Classroom Discourse Analysis (CDA) is the way to analyze what happen in the classroom between teacher and student and what make every student different in their language achievement. Shortly, classroom discourse analysis is language that teachers and student use in classroom. Benham is a town in the United Kingdom (2009) Classroom discourse is a sort of discussion that takes place in classrooms. Unequal power connections, speaking turns, interaction patterns, and other characteristics of classroom discourse can be found.

A classroom discourse, according to Gee (2011), is a distinctive method of saying, doing, and being. You use the resources of English to present oneself as a specific sort of person, a different kind in different circumstances, when you speak or write anything. Here the language that use should be analyze as a good structure to get the meaning and the purpose why that language produce. This classroom discourse analysis is study about the language in use of written text in any vary, the spoken data that convey even from a simple conversation till the high institutional forms of speech in the classroom between teacher and students. Classroom discourse analysis study, according to Allwright (1983), is simply research centered on classroom interaction that focuses on the inputs or outputs to the classroom. It just tries to figure out what happens when students and teachers join together in the classroom (Hinkel, 2004).

However, Johnstone (2002) stated that Text messages and sign language are both forms of dialogue. Discourse, on the other hand, is made up of bigger language units than those studied in classical linguistic analysis, and it deals with themes such as linguistic performance and sociolinguistics.

There is no indication that what is unsaid is not understood; rather, 'unsaid' indicates 'but understood nonetheless,' and another way of referring to ellipsis is as something understood, where understood is used in the particular sense of 'going without saying.' Holiday and Hasan (Halliday and Hasan, 2004)

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2. *Initiation-Response-Feedback (IRF)*

The morpheme is at the bottom of the grammatical rank-scale in English grammar or linguistics, according to Halliday (2004), while the sentence is at the top. As a result, the linguistic grammatical rank scale goes from morpheme-word-group/clause-sentence to morpheme-word-group/clause-sentence. In a similar vein, Sinclair and Coulthard (1975) presented a five-unit discourse ranking system. We also have ACT-MOVE-EXCHANGE-TRANSACTION-LESSON, which goes from lowest to highest. This is illustration about the hierarchy of rank scale in Discourse:

Figure 1. The rank scale level of Sinclair and Coulthard

Based on the figure that display above, the rank start with the highest one, Lesson. So, Lesson is combine from many transactions. This part or lesson start from teachers enter the classroom, conveying the lesson till the teacher leaves the classroom, which in turn making a number of exchange. In other terms, a lesson can be described as a series of exchanges. At the very least, a transaction is a trade. In other words, a transaction might refer to a series of exchanges. Right, well, and good are some of the framing words that now serve as transaction boundaries. It's used to signal the end of one transaction and the start of another.

Next rank scale is Exchange. Here is the process of Initiation Response and Feedback appear. It start from the teacher Initiation, continue with the students response and follow by feedback to the students response by the teacher, that realize by eliciting, informing and directing moves. Moves will make an act. And act is the smallest part of analysis and have so many different functions.

a. Exchange

The term "exchange" refers to the "fundamental unit of interaction." It is fundamental because it is made up of only two participants' inputs and because it combines to generate the greatest unit of interaction, the transaction (as quoted in Coulthard, 1992).

A group of moves makes up an exchange. It refers to a situation in which participants in a conversation make a succession of movements. Depending on the situation, an exchange can include a query, an answer, a comment, or more. An exchange can be said to have occurred when the first speaker asks the next speaker a question, he responds, and the first speaker returns to deliver a follow-up. Consider the following illustration:

A: What time is it?
B: Twelve thirty.
A: Thanks.
Student A: Let's come tomorrow.
Student B: Oh yeah.
Student A: Yes.

There are three moves in each of these exchanges. 'What time is it?' is the first move, and it is a query. The first movement in (2) is seen as a request. Free exchanges, bound exchanges, opening exchanges, medical exchanges, and

closing exchanges are all examples of exchanges. It should be remembered, however, that exchanges might be as numerous as the discourses of various disciplines of study or vocation. Boundary exchanges and teaching exchanges are the two types of exchanges. Framing and focussing moves are included in boundary exchanges. In particular, the teaching exchange most usually occurs the sorts of teacher-students talking in the classroom, which is realized by the Initiation-Response-Feedback model (IRF). It starts from teacher Initiation or usually appear with the teacher question, followed by the students response or the students answer and followed by the teacher feedback. IRF challenge students to think, reason, and make connections.

(i) Initiation

As stated by Dayag (2008), initiation (I) is the movement in which a teacher initiates an interaction. Initiation (I) is the movement in which a teacher asks a question or takes an action to initiate students to interact in the classroom. It is the teacher's endeavor to encourage students to immerse themselves in a conversation or encounter. It is at this point, according to Harmer (2007), "that the teacher has to do something to get the kids involved, engaged, and ready." It is also thought to be a key approach to build an interactive language classroom since it gives stimulus for students to interact with one other on a regular basis.

(ii) Response

Following the teacher's introduction, the students' response (R) is what the pupils really do. According to Dayag et al (2008), the teacher initiates the response in response to the participants' initiation move. It indicates that pupils interact in response to the teacher's cues..

(iii) Feedback

Feedback/follow-up (F), the final exchange of a turn in which pupils are given feedback on their responses. According to Dayag et al. (2008), feedback completes the cycle by bringing the initiation and reaction to a close. It means that pupils receive immediate feedback or feedback on their responses.

Some research has looked at IRF and classroom engagement, and several have found that IRF can help teachers and students interact more actively in the classroom. In general, these research demonstrate that the IRF pattern is the most common type of interaction in the classroom. Nonetheless, the number of studies examining IRF reflection in classroom interaction and the prevailing exchange among I, R, and F is not nearly as large as the number of studies examining IRF use. As a result, the purpose of this study is to examine the IRF (Initiation-Response-Feedback) reflection in Reading class, as well as the prevailing interchange among I, R, and F. I (opening), R (response), and F (follow-up) moves are used in teaching exchanges.

b. Move

Acts merge to produce exchanges, which are made up of moves. Exchanges are made up of five different types of moves. Framing moves are used to structure the lesson and are frequently followed by focusing moves, which are used to draw students' attention to the lesson's direction. The remaining three actions are known as opening, answering, and following up.

The goal of a given opening could be to convey information, direct action, or elicit a fact. The first step is to invite students to engage in the discussion. The head act in the opening move determines the answering move, which is usually a student reaction.

Move is the unit of discourse that comes after act in terms of importance. It is divided into one or more acts. When the request is straightforward, such as 'give me the bag,' it can be straightforward. When there are too many demands in one, such as 'Dad, I need a school bag,' it can become complicated. Not only that, but try to stuff some note books within it as well. Don't forget to include a pen and two or more pencils as well. Some relevant texts should also be included. 'Do you think that's reasonable, or are my requests too much for you?' There are various types of movements. The following are some of them:

A. Opening and answering moves: An opening move is using to start a discourse. It can ask a question, give information, request something, direct an action. The opening move is often followed or accompanied by an answering move as an answer to the opening move.

Driver: Where do I drop you off? (Opening)

Driven: Just keep moving. I'll stop you when I get there. (Answering)

B. Focusing and framing moves: Focusing and framing moves are more commonly fins in the classroom situation. It can also be useful in a religious setting, for instance in the church where a sermon is to be preached. Focusing often comes before framing. Preacher: The topic of our sermon today is the end-time Christians (Focusing). However, before we go into that, we need to explain who a Christian is (Framing).

C. Feedback or follow-up move: the feedback or follow-up move acts as a judgment on the answering move. It's also really valuable in the classroom. It's when a teacher asks a question and then returns to analyze whether or not the question was asked correctly. To put it another way, the teacher makes a decision. Consider the following scenario:

Teacher: How many semesters make a session?

Student: Two semesters:

Teacher: Good of you. (follow-up move)

Following the answering move and in response to the student's response, the teacher often performs the follow-up move. This action is critical in determining whether or not the students have completed the task assigned to them by the teacher. With such significance, if the follow-up is not provided, the students may believe they have given the incorrect answer or that there is a problem.

Sinclair and Coulthard
Framing
Focusing
Opening
Answering
Follow up

Figure 2. Kinds of Move

Marker	M	'Well,' 'OK,' 'now,' 'good,' 'right,' and 'alright' are examples of closed classes of goods. Its purpose is to draw lines in the conversation.
Meta-statement	Ms	Realized by a statement that relates to a future time when the described event will take place. Its objective is to assist students in seeing the structure of the lesson, understanding the purpose of the succeeding exchange, and determining where they are heading.
Silent stress	^	Following a marker, there is a pause of one or more beats in length. When the marker is used as the head of a boundary exchange signaling a transaction boundary, it highlights the marker.
Accept	Acc	A closed class of items – "yes," "no," "good," "fine," and repeat of the pupil's response – is realized, all with neutral low fall intonation. Its purpose is to show that the teacher has heard or seen anything and that the informative, respond, or react was correct.
Acknowledge	Ack	Yes, OK, cor, mm, wow, and certain nonverbal movements and expressions are examples. Its sole purpose is to demonstrate that the learner has comprehended the commencement and, if the head was a directive, that the pupil intends to respond.
Check	Ch	Realized through a closed set of polar questions about being 'completed' or 'ready,' having 'issues' or 'difficulties,' and being able to 'see' or 'hear.' They're 'real' questions because the teacher doesn't know the answer for once. It is a command, not a check, if he knows the answer to a question like 'have you finished?' The purpose of checks is to allow the teacher to determine whether there are any issues that are stopping the session from progressing smoothly.
Clue	Cl	A statement, query, command, or moodless item causes this to happen. It reports to the head of the initiation and assists the learner in answering the elicitation or following the directive by supplying extra information.
Comment	Com	A statement or tag question is used to do this. Its job is to exemplify, expand, justify, and provide additional information and is subordinate to the move's head. On the printed page, it's difficult to tell the difference between an informative and a persuasive piece because outsiders' perceptions of relevance aren't necessarily the same. Teachers, on

		the other hand, utilize a pause to communicate that they are starting a new initiation with an informative as a head; otherwise, they are seen as commenting.
Directive	D	A command made it happen. Its purpose is to elicit a nonverbal response.
Elicitation	El	A command made it happen. Its purpose is to elicit a nonverbal response.
Evaluate	E	Statements and tag questions with words and phrases like 'good,' 'interesting,' 'team point,' commenting on the quality of the reply, react, or initiation, as well as 'yea,' 'no,' 'good,' 'fine,' with a high-fall intonation, and the repetition of the pupil's reply with either high-fall (positive) or any kind of rise (negative evaluation)
Informative	I	A statement has brought this to fruition. It is distinct from other meanings of the word "statement" in that its main purpose is to convey information. The only way to respond is to admit that you've been paying attention and that you comprehend what's going on.
Prompt	P	'Go on,' 'come on,' 'hurry up,' 'quickly,' 'makes a guess' are examples of closed classes of goods. Its purpose is to emphasize a command or elicitation by implying that the teacher is anticipating or even demanding a response rather than requesting one.
React	Rea	A non-linguistic activity brought it about. Its purpose is to offer a non-linguistic answer that is appropriate for the elicitation.
Reply	Rep	A statement, query, or moodless item, as well as nonverbal surrogates such as nods, are used to achieve this. Its purpose is to produce an acceptable linguistic response to the elicitation.
Starter	S	A statement, query, or demand causes it to happen. Its purpose is to convey information about, draw attention to, or guide thought to a certain location in order to increase the likelihood of a proper response to the initiation.
Cue	Cu	'Hands up, don't call out,' and 'is John the only one' are examples of a closed class of objects of which we have only three exponents so far. Its sole purpose is to elicit a suitable bid.
Bid	B	'Sir,' 'Miss,' teacher's name, raised hand, heavy breathing, finger clicking – a closed class of verbal and non-verbal components – Its purpose is to indicate a desire to participate in the conversation.

Nominate	N	'You,' with contrastive stress, 'anybody,' 'yea,' and one or two idiosyncratic items, such as 'who hasn't said anything yet,' are realized by a closed class consisting of all the students' names, 'you,' with contrastive stress, 'anybody,' 'yea,' and one or two idiosyncratic items, such as 'who hasn't said anything. The purpose of nomination is to invite or allow a student to participate in the discussion.
Aside	Z	A moodless statement, query, or demand is made, usually with a lower voice tone, and is not truly addressed to the class. As previously said, this category includes topics that we find tough to cope with. It's basically just the teacher talking to himself, saying things like, 'It's chilly in here.' 'Can you tell me where I put my chalk?'

3. Classroom Interaction

Interaction is synonymous with the learning process itself (Allwright, 2008). Interaction can develop and increase the student ability in language, even spoken or written. They will hear some new vocabulary from the others and applied it in their daily life. Interaction is the hearth of communication (Douglas, 2001:1:165). It can said that when someone convey a message, receiving the message, translate or interpreting it, and make a negotiating meaning.

They must interact frequently in the target language in order to gain expertise in English communication, as contact is the essence of communication (Brown, 2000). Interaction occurs anywhere and at any time, including in the classroom, as long as individuals are interacting with one another and doing action and receiving reply from one another. Dagarin (2004: 128) argues that classroom interaction is "two ways process between the participants in the language process, the teacher influences the learners and vice versa. Furthermore, classroom interaction is classified as pedagogic interaction, which refers to interactions that occur throughout the teaching and learning process.

Unfortunately, it appears that using the target language all of the time in the language classroom is challenging, especially in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classes. This has occurred because EFL students share a similar native language (Brown, 2000). If an EFL teacher overlooks it, the purpose of the teaching process will be missed. As a result, by impressing the students with the need of English practice for future success and telling them that it can help them strengthen their intuition for language, the usage of native language when interacting can be reduced (Brown, 2000). Firstly, it can increase students' knowledge of language. Rivers (1987) notes that, "Through interaction, students can increase their language store as they listen to or read authentic linguistic material, or even the out puts of their fellow students, in discussions, skits, joint problem-solving tasks, or dialogue journals...". Second, it has the ability to strengthen social bonds. Students' relationships will be strengthened by

interaction, either among themselves or with their teachers, because it allows them to learn from one another and receive feedback on their performance (Naimat, 2011). Thirdly, it is beneficial to develop students' communicative skill. According to Thapa and Lin (2013), "interaction in the classroom becomes the central factor which is able to enhance the students' linguistic resources as well as equipping them with appropriate skills for communication." (Naimat, 2011) "The communication skill, then, will be acquired through speaking activities, such as debates, discussions and about desired topics among students." Finally, it helps kids gain confidence in speaking. "Interaction is a vital social activity for students in the language classroom," Thapa and Lin (2013) write, "through which they not only develop information, but also establish confidence and identity as competent language users."

4. Reading Skills

There some definition about Reading by experts. As we know reading is the acquisition the information then sent to mind and then processes. Reading is a dynamic, interactive, and global activity including learnt abilities, according to Leu and Kinzer (1987: 9). This is the process of conveying meaning, often known as the information gathering process.

Furthermore, reading is a procedure carried out and used by a reader to acquire a message that is delivered by a writer through words that may be seen and known by the reader, according to Tarigan (2008: 7). In a nutshell, reading is the process of learning something new to refresh our minds, also known as the process of going from not knowing to knowing.

A general notion of reading may be gleaned from all of the definitions above as an active process of gaining meaning. Knowledge drives this process, which is impacted by nonlinguistic internal and external circumstances. Aside from that, reading can be considered a life skill that is relevant to both immediate and long-term success, and reading is generally used as a source of information and enjoyment.

5. Narrative Text

Narrative text is a text that contains several problems and finally find the solution in last event. This text is purpose to entertain the reader while reading this text. Actually this text use in education or in lesson because it easy to interest the students and invite the student to make an imagination.

According to Keraf in Nurhidayah (2017) states that "Narrative text as a story tells or describes an action in the past time clearly. In addition, according to Pratyasto, narrative text is a type of text that is purposed to amuse and to deal with actual and various experience in different ways, narrative text also deals with problematic events which lead to a crisis or turning points of kind, which in turn find a resolution.

In short, narrative text use a complete explanation of a problem. Start from the introduction of all the character, the problem till the solving of problem. Although a narrative text written for its own sake-that is simply to recount events in most college writing narrative text is use for purpose, and a sequence of events is presenting to prove a point. The social purpose of this

type the text is entertaining because they deal with the unusual and unexpected development of events. It also instruct because they teach readers and listeners that problems patterns of behavior that re generally highly valued.

Therefore, narrative text is string to answer the question: what is happen?" Narrative text as a story, so it is should have the element that makes the story more interesting such a conflict and conclusion of the story.

6. *Online Class*

Online learning is a type of remote learning, often known as online education, that has long been a component of the American educational system and has recently grown to become the largest sector of distance learning (Bartley & Golek, 2004). Nowadays, the classroom not only happen face-to-face but also held by using a media to make an interaction. This research using online class as a place for teacher and students make an interaction. An online class is a course conducted over the Internet. Computer-based learning, web-based learning, virtual classrooms, and digital collaborations are all examples of online learning, which is a subset of distant education that encompasses a wide range of technological applications and learning processes (Urdan and Weggen 2000).

Many academics and educators believe that online learning can help to combat rising postsecondary education costs by spreading the cost of a class over a much larger number of students than traditional classrooms, dividing the cost by tens or hundreds of thousands of students rather than a few dozen (Bartley & Golek, 2004). Moreover, the marginal cost of a student in an online setting is negligible relative to the traditional setting, necessarily constrained by a number of factors such as the size and availability of the physical classroom. Shortly, online class is the process conveying the lesson using the media to build the interaction.

METHODOLOGY

In conducted this research, the writer used Descriptive Qualitative Research. Hancock, Ockleford, & Windridge (2009) claimed that qualitative research aimed to help us to understood the social world in which we lived and why things are the way they are. To get the data, the researcher did observation and used some instruments such as recording and interviewing to answered the research questions. This research was intended to describe the initiation, respond and feedback in reading that happened in the classroom. The research took the data using descriptive qualitative from the interaction in classroom by observation, recording every meeting from the beginning till the end, and also by interviewing. Recording done using zoom as the media to record because the research observe in the online English class. The first data got from the field is the transcriptions that consist from the result of observation in the class between the teacher and students. The data of this research collected used audio recording, video recording observation, and interview. Audio recording and video recording used to capture the speaking interaction between teacher and students in the classroom. Researcher used documentation and interviewing as the tools. While in technique to collecting the data, researcher used observation.

The technique of analyzing data use Miles and Huberman analysis model. The analysis consist of three steps, they are data condensation, data display, and drawing conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Findings

Type of IRF pattern used between teacher and students in Narrative Text

Table 2. Classroom interaction in Teaching Narrative Text
 (Starting the Lesson)

Speaker	Conversation	Interaction
Teacher	Good Morning students? How's a lives?	Initiation
Student	Good Morning Miss. I'm fine, thank you, and you?	Response
Teacher	Thanks God I'm good. Siapa yang belum join ini? Tolong diperhatikan sinyal nya ya. jangan nanti setengah-setengah keluar. Ms ga suka begitu dan bilang biar diizinkan masuk. Siapa yang keluar-keluar nanti ms ga kasih masuk lagi karna mengganggu konsentrasi dan pembelajaran.	Feedback

It can be seen from the first conversation, which is started from the teacher giving conversation that greeted students as the common conversation that start from the teacher as the leader in the class. This interaction called as Initiation (I). After teacher greeted the students the students would answered teacher greeted, this interaction called as a Response (R) to the Initiation. After the Response given by the students, next interaction as common in daily life school interaction used zoom is teacher make sure that students already joined the link (F). Commonly, the initiation started with the question to the other speaker to have a feedback with the Initiation.

All the interaction in the classroom usually get all the pattern. It can be seen, when the teacher starts the conversation towards the lessons, students can answer the teacher orally. But, some of the teacher initiation not got the responses from the students at all. Student sometimes only silently, or just focus to their books. Seems that condition appear, teacher repeated and make the explanation become simple until the students understand or become using Indonesia.

Not only focused in IRF pattern, teacher should be pay attention with the materials, which is reading a narrative text. The reading skill improved the kids' comprehension and provided some word knowledge. So, if the students do not grasp the content presented by the teacher, they will ask the teacher, and this is how the dialogue and IRF interaction in the classroom develop. However, in this study, the researcher concentrated on reading because it is when pupils begin to read a book that their curiosity emerges.

Based on the research on the field, it found that the students interest with the material, because it is related with their daily activity, such as what they did when the holiday comes. After that, when teacher explains the generic

structure, students pay attention, even some of the students should be leave the room because their network error.

Initiation-Response-Feedback is the pattern usually appeared in the classroom interaction, even Offline or Online class. This study focused in online class, as the field to get the result. There are some differences and similarities interaction in the classroom between online and offline class according to the researcher. The differences are students can't response teacher question orally, caused error network in the online class, but the offline class students and teacher can response each other orally. It can be seen that Response is not always shown by any words, but can be shown by the gestures too. So, if the class held like online class, teacher can't analyzed how's the students gestures or body language. The other differences are students in offline class can get all their needed about the lesson without limited by something. But in online class, students who can't have a good facility, such as a good electronic even network can't got anything from the lesson. In some similarities, it can be seen that all the participants even teacher or students can convey their confuses, discussion, even something wanted to say at that place even in online or offline.

To enhance the teaching and learning process, a healthy relationship between the teacher and the students should be established in the classroom. When a teacher is unable to hold a student's attention, the entire pattern of classroom interaction may be influenced. The teacher, as the primary player in classroom contact, should be able to facilitate it. When it comes to teaching English, some students struggle to express the topic itself. It can be concluded that it was caused by students' inability to communicate and grasp what the teacher was saying. The first cause students have low ability in English is they seldom to listened English in their daily live, it can be concluded that students environment not supported their willingness to spoke or have conversation students only listened how English spoken or written only in school, while in their daily live they using Indonesian. It looked when researcher join the online class, students have difficulties to answered teacher question in English, so they choose using Bahasa to response it. Second cause is students fear and confidence bigger than their willingness. It can be seen when researcher did the observation, some of students laughed when some of them wrong in pronoun the words.

Every interaction in the class, it's always started from teacher Initiation as the beginning to stimulate students' brain. Its form might be like a question and then students would answer it with giving a response by their opinion towards teacher feedback. The percentage of IRF pattern in the classroom interaction for learning narrative and Reading Narrative text can be seen in this table 4.17 below

Table 3. IRF Pattern

No	Type	Observation	
		Narrative Text	Reading Comprehension
1.	Teacher	38%	38%

	Initiation		
2.	Students Response	36%	38%
3.	Teacher Feedback	26%	24%
	Total	100%	100%

How to get the result is:

$$\text{Teacher Initiation} = \frac{\text{Teacher Initiation}}{\text{All the conversation}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Students Response} = \frac{\text{Students Responses}}{\text{All the conversation}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Teacher Feedback} = \frac{\text{Teacher Feedback}}{\text{All the conversation}} \times 100\%$$

From the table above, it can be concluded that in the first result was learning Narrative text in online class, the teacher Initiation was high, but student responses is higher than the teacher initiation. Students looked like enthusiast to know it, and have several questioned to ask with the teacher, it can be seen in the conversation about how many kinds of text that they knew, and kinds of tenses too. Although the have some difficulties to quest the right answer, but they already understand some of kind of the other subject that they ever heard, that's kinds students willingness to answered it. It can be concluded that students have a good memories to remember their previous lesson.

Teacher feedback is lowest one compared with the other pattern. This pattern is positioned in the last pattern, because this pattern is the way to give the right or make sure the initiation given by the teacher to student respond. When a student replies teacher question, the other students might be not hear clearly, or students answered is not good. So this is the way for teacher for make sure or tells the real answer to the students. Even this is the lowest one, but this is the important one in this pattern if compare between initiations and respond.

The other discussion as the result that research found based on the research is from the students comprehension in reading text, that shown from the IRF patter. Initiation giving by teacher has same percentage with student responses. It can be concluded that students already understand about narrative text, and when teacher gave exercise, they already knew how to did it. Even the tenses used and how to make the generic structure in narrative text. Student enthusiast appear and has a same percentage with teacher initiation is a good progress. It can be concluded that they are gave attention with the explanation and understand it well.

The other result according to online class that still having many troubles even for teacher and students. It can be seen, in the first interaction in classroom that teacher command in strict that anyone from the students who left the meeting, teacher would not give permit to join the class zoom again. Even there is network trouble, teacher not really care about that. Based on the interviewed that researcher done, teacher said that sometimes students said that they have a problem with the network, but actually they lazy to join the online class. So, teacher gave a strict role to make students become discipline and there is no other reason to be absent except students has illness. They will be forced to have a good signal for the zoom class.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aims of this study is to found out the type of IRF pattern used between teacher and students while reading a narrative text and to analyzed how was the realization of IRF in classroom interaction. Following the analysis of the research findings and discussion in the previous chapter, the following conclusion can be drawn:

1. The type of IRF pattern used in classroom interaction based on Sinclair and Coulthard 1975 is used all. Even the initiation, Response and feedback. The three of that pattern is related each other. Started from teacher Initiation, continued to students responses, even teacher don't have any response at first, it should be repeated with giving other initiation. After that should be followed by feedback. Even from all the analyses, feedback is lowest interaction in the classroom.
2. The realization of the IRF pattern itself already used in the classroom. Even the percentage of three of them not balances, but the interaction still running well.
3. The language employed in the classroom by the teacher and pupils were unbalanced.

Only 37% teacher and students use English, while 63% use Bahasa. Actually, in teaching and learning process, if talking about teacher ability in managed the class, teacher can did it well. Teacher able to get student attention to listen teachers explanation in front of the class. The one and only problem there in student low abilities to caught up the material if teacher use English. From interviewed and observation done in that school, it also caused of students has a limited vocabulary in English.

FURTHER STUDY

The limitation in this article is that the discussion of the article has a limited scope. In addition, the limitations in this study only discuss the study of education management.

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